

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

ENGLISH IDIOMS AND THEIR TRANSLATION PROPORTION IN ARMENIAN

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7271265>

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Abstract

The focal interest of the research is based on the relevance of “naturalness” in Armenian translations of English botanical idioms. Special attention is paid to the methods of translation and interpretation of these culturally marked units in the target language.

Our study is one-directional, taking English as starting point and is based on the analysis of synchronic research data. More often we encountered difficulties stemming from the lack of rich translation data in Armenian and in this case our comparative analysis was interwoven with a cross-linguistic one. Such an approach enabled us to get more valuable insights into the study of the linguistic phenomenon.

Keywords: botanical idioms, “naturalness”, proportion, disproportion, equivalence

Before embarking upon a detailed description of botanical idioms it is of great significance to make a demarcation line on the one hand between various types of multiword combinations (MWU) and idiomatic expressions, and on the other hand, between idiom and idiomaticity.

The difference in terminology (“set-phrases”, “idioms”, “word-equivalents”) reflects certain differences in the main criteria used to distinguish types of *phraseological units and free word groups*. The term “set phrase” implies that the basic criterion of differentiation is the stability of the lexical components and grammatical structure of word groups. The term “idiom” generally implies that the essential feature of the linguistic units is idiomaticity or lack of motivation. The term “word-equivalent” stresses not only semantic but also functional inseparability of certain word groups, their aptness to function in speech as single words (D.N. Davletbaeva, 2010).

‘Idiomaticity’ is used ambiguously in the literature. It represents both the quality of being marked by idioms, as well as the ability to speak a fluent and appropriate version of a language (A.Makkai 1969, p.23). The terms ‘idiom’ or “type one idiomaticity” and ‘idiomaticity’ or “type two idiomaticity” (Alexander, 1987), although related, are not identical. The second term ‘idiomaticity’ applies to how a native speaker of a language successfully combines words, or units of language, in a native-like manner, or “a particular manner of expressing something in a language, music, art, and so on, which characterizes a person or group” (Moon, 1998, p.3). ‘Idiomaticity’ is also demonstrated by Sinclair’s ‘idiom principle’, giving a language user a choice of using a number of semi-preconstructed phrases rather than stringing together individual words.

The essential features of phraseological units are: a) lack of semantic motivation; b) lexical and grammatical stability. As far as *semantic motivation* is concerned phraseological units are extremely varied from motivated (by simple addition of denotational meaning) *like a sight for sore eyes* and *to know the ropes* to partially motivated (when one of the words is used in a not

direct meaning) or to demotivated (completely non-motivated) *like tit for tat*, *red-tape*. *Lexical and grammatical stability of phraseological units* is displayed in the fact that no substitution of any elements whatever is possible in the following stereotyped (unchangeable) set expressions, which differ in many other respects: *all the world and his wife*, *calf love*, *heads or tails*, *first night*, *to gild the pill*, *to hope for the best*, *busy as a bee*, *fair and square*, *stuff and nonsense* *time and again* (D.N. Davletbaeva, 2010).

N.N. Amosova’s approach is contextological. She defines phraseological units as units of fixed context. Fixed context is defined as a context characterised by a specific and unchanging sequence of definite lexical components, and a peculiar semantic relationship between them. Units of fixed context are subdivided into phrasemes and idioms. Phrasemes are always binary: one component has a phraseologically bound meaning, the other serves as the determining context (*small talk*, *small hours*, *small change*). In idioms the new meaning is created by the whole, though every element may have its original meaning weakened or even completely lost: *in the nick of time* (meaning: at the exact moment). Idioms may be motivated or demotivated. A motivated idiom is homonymous to a free phrase, but this phrase is used figuratively: *take the bull by the horns* ‘to face dangers without fear’. *In the nick of time* is demotivated, because the word *nick* is obsolete. Both phrasemes and idioms may be movable (changeable) or immovable (D.N. Davletbaeva, 2010).

Considerable work on idioms has been done by lexicographers (Cowie & Mackin, 1975; Cowie et al., 1983; Sinclair & Moon, 1989, 1995), Eastern European phraseologists (Arnold, 1973; Lipka, 1991; Mel’cuk, 1988; Mel’cuk, Arbatchewsky-Jumarie, Elnitsky, Iordanskaja, & Lessard, 1984), lexical semanticists (Cruse, 1986), lexicologists (Carter, 1987), and researchers into vocabulary in language teaching (Carter & McCarthy, 1988). The criterion used most often to define idioms is the one related to their *noncompositionality*. In other words, the meaning of idioms cannot be predicted from the meaning of their constituent parts.

Some idiomatic strings have both a literal and a non-literal meaning (*kick the bucket*: 'strike the pail with your foot', *kick the bucket* = 'die'; *bread and butter*: 'two food items', bread and butter = 'main income-producing activity'; *red tape*: 'coloured ribbon', *red tape* = 'excessive bureaucracy'), contextual clues may be necessary to distinguish whether the MWU has a literal or idiomatic interpretation. The term 'literal' is being used here as "nonmetaphorical literality: directly meaningful language – not language that is understood, even partly, in terms of something else" (Lakoff, 1986, p.292). Moon finds the literal meanings of such phrases as above are always rarer than the idiomatic interpretation, while others (Cowie et al., 1983, p.xiii) go so far as to claim that the literal senses of expressions such as *beat one's breast* and *burn one's boats* "do not survive alongside their figurative ones in normal, everyday use" (Moon, 1998).

Although several criteria have been suggested in the literature to define (or more accurately – describe) idioms and various other MWUs, lists of idioms in dictionaries and teaching texts nevertheless provide a heterogeneous set of items under this all-encompassing heading. In the past, the most commonly accepted of the criteria for defining idioms included some or all of these criteria (Fernando & Flavell, 1981, p.17):

1. the meaning of an idiom is not the result of the compositional function of its constituents;
2. an idiom is a unit that either has a homonymous literal counterpart or at least individual constituents that are literal, though the expression as a whole would not be interpreted literally;
3. idioms are transformationally deficient in one way or another;
4. idioms constitute set expressions in a given language;
5. idioms are institutionalized.

Idioms as multifaceted linguistic units can pose difficulties both with their study and with their translation.

In order to overcome all possible difficulties in translating idioms some effective strategies should be adopted.

Generally, different translation strategies are singled out by different translation theorists. Overall they suggest translating idioms with non-idioms, translating idioms with idioms and translating idioms literally. Nida and Taber (1982) exclude the literal translation strategy and suggest three translation strategies for idioms: translating idioms with non-idioms, translating idioms with idioms and translating non-idioms with idioms. Nida and Taber claim that most frequently source language idioms can be translated with target language non-idioms, although they also admit that sometimes it is indeed possible by an equivalent target language idiom though it should be highlighted that idioms suffer a great deal of semantic adjustment. The most recommended translated strategy for idioms is translating them with a natural target language idiom which has the same meaning as the original language idiom. Bassnett – McGuire (1980), on the other hand, suggest that an idiom should be translated on the basis of the function

of the phrase: the source language idiom should be replaced by a target language idiom that has the same meaning and function in TL culture. As distinct from this Newmark (1981) proposes that the original SL idiom and its translation should be equally frequent in two languages. This approach is somewhat impossible since it is rather difficult to estimate the frequency of certain expression in certain languages.

Another view on translation idioms is by Baker. M. Baker, in her book "In other words" (1992) presents five strategies which can help overcome the difficulties faced while the translation of idiomatic expressions:

1. Using an idiom of similar meaning and form

This strategy, which seems the best, involves using an idiom in the target language which transmits the same meaning as that of the source-language idiom and, besides, consists of corresponding lexical items. For example, *más vale tarde que nunca* in Spanish means *better late than never* in English, both of these idioms have similar meaning and form. There is also an Armenian version of the idiom, which is լավ է ուշ քան երբեք. Unfortunately, this type of match can only occasionally be achieved.

2. Using an idiom of similar meaning but dissimilar form

It is likely to come across an idiom or fixed expression in the target language which has a meaning similar to that of the source idiom or expression, but whose lexical items are different. For example, the Spanish expression *Dios los cria y ellos se juntan* ('*God breeds them and they gather together*') and the English expression *birds of a feather flock together* use different lexical items to express more or less the same idea.

3. Translation by paraphrase

This is one of the most popular strategies of dealing with translation of idioms. It is usually used when two matching idioms in the source and the target language cannot be found or when their uses are slightly different depending on the context, in a way that it could affect the style of the text.

Paraphrases might be quite accurate when it is important for the translator to transfer the form and the meaning without omitting and eliminating any elements. One of such Spanish idioms, that have to be paraphrased when translated, is *arrimar el ascua a su sardina* (*to bring coals or embers to one's sardine*) which really means to put one's own interests first, to work things to one's advantage, in other words, every man for himself.

4. Translation by omission

In the case of omission, also called translation by ellipsis, the idiom may be omitted altogether. According to Baker (1992, p.77) omission is allowed only when there is no close equivalent in the target language or it is difficult to paraphrase as well as an idiom may be omitted for stylistic reasons.

5. Translation by compensation

This strategy is difficult to describe or illustrate. The strategy of compensation means that in some such situations the translator may omit the idiomaticity of a certain expression in the source text and introduce it elsewhere in the target text. This strategy is supposed to make up any loss of meaning and not to alter the

emotional force or the stylistic effect of the source text. It positively affects the vocabulary richness of the target text.

A good translation is a translation that uses all of the above strategies to deal with idioms. Using the typical phraseology, such as natural collocations, fixed phrases and semi-fixed expressions from the target language may seem to be a big challenge for the translator but it actually enhances the quality and the readability of the translation. A good translation should not only sound less ‘foreign’ but also feel as if it were original. A good translation “may even pass for an original” (Baker, 1992, p. 78).

Thus, idioms being very culture-specific and grammatically peculiar speech forms have always been at the center of attention of both foreign language learners and translators. The meaning of idioms is deemed the main cause for confusion and failure to attain the accurate and appropriate translation. Nonetheless, it is up to the language learners and translators to cultivate their language skills to such an extent and achieve such a level that will allow breaking all the language barriers and open a whole world of metaphorically used expressions, which will make the communication far more exciting and enjoyable.

In the further step of our research we shall dwell upon the translation of English botanical idioms with plant food (legume) and plant components in Armenian.

• **Bean:** edible seed or seedpod of certain leguminous plants of the family Fabaceae. The genera (genus) *Phaseolus* and *Vigna* have several species each of well-known beans, though a number of economically important species can be found in various genera throughout the family (Britannica).

(*To spill the beans* – գաղտնիքներն ասել, բերանը/ բերանում լոբի չթրջվել)

The idiom of interest is “(*to spill the beans*)” and the definition is *to tell people secret information* (Cambridge dictionary). This idiom is one of the most widely used idioms in our paper. According to the Scholastic Dictionary of Idioms, by Marvin Terban, this probably dates back to ancient Greece when people would use beans to vote anonymously. White beans were used for positive votes, and for negative votes, black beans or other dark-colored beans were used. These votes were cast in secret, so if someone knocked over the beans in the jar—whether by accident or intentionally—they “*spilled the beans*” and revealed the results of the votes prematurely (Readers Digest). This idiom can be semantically defined a pure idiom. Pure idioms (Cowie, 1988; Fernando & Flavell, 1981) include those that have both a literal and a no literal meaning. They have also been described as ‘well-formed’ idioms (Chafe, 1968) an ‘idioms of decoding’ (Makkai, 1972). In other words, this idiomatic sense has nothing to do with beans, and the action of spilling the beans is possible. Here is an extracted example from “Hearts of Three” by Jack London.

And Henry literally went up in the air.

“You can’t step on my ear, Torres!” he shouted, at the same time dropping him, as he had dropped the priest with his right hook.

“And now the beans are spilled,” Francis commented in dry and spiritless disgust. “The Sun God stuff is finished right here and now.” [152]

Հենրին տառաջհորեն թռավ օդի մեջ:

- Բնչպե՞ս էս համարձակվում, Թորես, - քղալեց նա, Թորեսին շարտելով գետին, ինչպես քիչ առաջ քուրմին էր գետին շարտել:

- Դե, այժմ ամեն ինչ կորավ, - հուսահատորեն հառաչեց Ֆրենսիսը: [465]

It is up to the translator to decide what techniques of translation should be used in a given case. In the above-given utterance the English idiomatic expression is completely omitted and this loss is felt both in the plane of context and that of evaluative effect. In the target utterance could be used an Armenian idiomatic expression “բերանը/ բերանում լոբի չթրջվել” - to tell/let out all the secrets (Idiomatic dictionary, 1971). The choice of this equivalent would nicely fit the context both in meaning and its structure. The architecture of Armenian phrase embraces the same constituent (լոբի-bean). The similarity is possible due to the reference of ancient Greek hypothesis about voting with beans.

• **Seed:** a small, round or oval object produced by a plant and from which, when it is planted, a new plant can grow (Cambridge dictionary).

Go to seed – մաշված, անտեսված, մոռացված

The idiom “*go to seed*”, also is used as “*run to seed*” and with other tenses of go (*went/gone/ going to seed*) means - showing signs of advanced wear and tear and neglect; to become worse or of less value. The expression *go to seed* was first used in a literal sense to describe a plant that has become neglected or is at the end of its life cycle, when it produces seeds and then dies. The idiom is semantically a full idiom, as the constituent or series of constituents contains no formatives whose ordinary lexical meaning contributes to the semantic interpretation (Newmeyer, 1974). The idiom came into use in the latter-1700s. The example is extracted from *Hearts of Three* by Jack London.

“Sounds like a queer sort of Spanish,” Francis observed.

“It’s medieval, to say the least,” Leoncia confirmed.

“It’s the Spanish of the conquistadores pretty badly gone to seed,” Torres contributed. “You see I was right. The Lost Souls never get away.” [145]

- Նրանց լեզուն նման է իսպաներենին, միայն թե մի տեսակ տարօրինակ է, - նկատեց Ֆրանսիսը:

- Դա պարզապես միջնադարյան իսպաներեն է, ուրիշ ոչինչ, - հաստատեց Լեոնսիան:

- Այդ լեզվով խոսում էին կոնկիստադորները, բայց այժմ արդեն ոչ ոք չի հիշում, - ավելացրեց Թորեսը: - Տեսնու՞մ էք, էս իրավացի էի: Այն ժամանակներից Կորուսյալ Հոգիները ենթեք չեն հեռացել հովտից: [454]

The idiom “gone to seed” is transformed into a free combination in the target passage (“ոչ ոք չի հիշում”); having lost its idiomatic labelling.

Seed(s) of desire - ցանկության սերմեր

The idiom “seeds of desire” can be originated from another idiomatic expression “(to) sow the seeds of something” (also *plant the seeds of something*), and the definition - to start the process which causes a particular problem or benefit to develop (Collins dictionary). The word “something” gives us an opportunity to replace it with other words for creating relevant situations as the pronoun implies general meaning. For example, “seeds of doubt”, “seeds of disaster” and such expressions can be found in the English language. Semantically, the idiom can be defined as a semi-opaque idiom, where the meaning is not as easy, but may be possible to guess (Fernando & Flavell, 1981). Here is an example with the discussed idiom:

And whether I yielded to drink, as at Benicia, or whether I refrained, as at the laundry, in my brain the seeds of desire for alcohol were germinating. [84]

Բայց և այնպես, չնայած լվացքատանը չէի ենթարկվում ողելից խմիչքի հրապույրին, ինչպես այն ժամանակ Բենիշիուիս, սակայն ցանկության սերմերը հասունանում էին իմ ուղեղում: [150]

This is a figurative idiomatic expression, and the same effect can be observed in the Armenian variant of the translation. The method of translation is the similar form with similar sense.

• **Tree:** woody plant that regularly renews its growth (perennial). Most plants classified as trees have a single self-supporting trunk containing woody tissues, and in most species the trunk produces secondary limbs, called branches (Britannica).

The foot of a tree – ծառի ներքևի հատվածը

The expression “foot of a tree” comes from the expression “foot of something”. The word foot has a connotative meaning “something resembling a foot in position or use; lower part” (Merriam Webster dictionary), and some other relevant expressions can be found in the English language: *foot of the stairs/ladder; the foot of a mountain/cliff, the foot of the altar, etc.* This idiomatic expression can be semantically classified as a semi-idiom, that is, a phrase where at least one word contributes its literal meaning (Cowie, 1981; Newmeyer, 1974; Weinreich, 1969). The following example is from *The Mysterious Island* by Jules Verne.

The sailor and the lad, creeping among the grass, arrived at the foot of a tree, whose lower branches were covered with little birds. The couroucous were waiting the passage of insects which served for their nourishment. Their feathery feet could be seen clasping the slender twigs which supported them. [33]

Նավաստին և պատանին զգուշությամբ մոտեցան մի ծառի, որի ճյուղերը ծածկված էին այդ թռչուններով, սրանք միջատներ էին որսում: Նրանք իրենց մահակները մանգաղի պես շարժելով, զարկեցին այդ թռչունների շարքերին, և հարյուրի չափ թռչուններ գետին թափվեցին: Սկզբում այդ հիմար թռչնակները

չէին փորձում անգամ թռչել, և դրանից հետո միայն մնացածները թռան այդ վտանգավոր տեղից: [36]

The idiomatic expression is translated into a single word which collocates with the indefinite article “մի”. The mission of the article in this case is intensification - to emphasize the meaning of the noun (ծառ) standing in postposition to the article.

(Green) Wave of trees and bushes – ծառերի ու թփերի (կանաչ) ալիքը

The expression is similar to the previous expression as they are semantically semi-idioms. The expression is taken from *The Scarlet Plague*.

The forest on either side swelled up the slopes of the embankment and crested across it in a green wave of trees and bushes. [11]

Երկու կողմից թմբին էր մոտենում անտառը, ծառերն ու թփերը ձգվում էին լանջերն ի վեր, և կանաչ ալիքը վրա տվեց գազանների արահետին: [625]

The part of this extract conveys the emotive evaluation rather vividly. Clearly, the exploitation of words “green” and “wave” in the structure of the idiomatic expression makes the passage vivid through amplifying attitudinal force. In the process of translating the translator needs to take into account both macro (genre, readership, etc.) and micro factors (structure of languages, the resources available in the target language). The translator found it appropriate to create somehow a new structure of the sentence for making it comprehensible for the Armenian readership.

Beds of seaweed - ջրախոտերի շերտ

The starting point of the study should be the constituent “bed”. Apart from the generally known meaning of the word “bed” (a piece of furniture on or in which to lie and sleep), it also has other meanings as *a flat or level surface; a plot of ground prepared for plants; the bottom of a body of water; a mass or heap resembling a bed; a supporting surface or structure* (Merriam Webster dictionary). As for the second constituent “seaweed” it pertains its denotational meaning: *a green, brown, or dark red plant that grows in the sea or on land very close to the sea* (Cambridge dictionary). The idiom is from the novel “*The Mysterious Island*”.

The sea had left unquestionable traces of its ravages. Sweeping over the islet, it had furiously assailed the passages, half filling them with sand, while thick beds of seaweed covered the rocks. [133]

Ծովի վայրագության հետքերը խիստ նկատելի էին Գարկառում: Օվկիանոսի սհազին կռահակներն անցնելով Փրկության կղզու վրայով՝ Գարկառի միջանցքների հատակը ծածկել էին ջրախոտերի հաստ շերտով: [163]

The selected designation of those two phrases are close to each other, specifically the linguistic unit “bed”, “շերտ” implies in this context the meaning “a supporting surface or structure” and the compound noun “seaweed” is moulded in Armenian in the similar vein.

Heart of the bush – թփի կենտրոնական մասը

Focusing on the component “heart”, in the Cambridge dictionary it has another meaning other than anatomical denotational meaning, which is “the central or most important part”. The example with the expression (heart of the bush) is from “White Fang”. Semantically the idiom is semi-opaque (the meaning is not as easy, but may be possible, to guess).

The rotten bark gave way under his feet, and with a despairing yelp he pitched down the rounded crescent, smashed through the leafage and stalks of a small bush, and in the heart of the bush, on the ground, fetched up in the midst of seven ptarmigan chicks. [53]

Նա փորձեց անցնել տապալված սոճու բնով. փտած կեղևը տեղի տվեց նրա ոտքերի տակ, և նա հուսակտուր վնգստարով՝ պոկվեց կլոր բնից, ընկավ թփի վրա և գլորվելով տերնների ու ճյուղերի միջով՝ իրեն գտավ հենց բույնի մեջ, որտեղ նստել էին կաքավի յոթ ձագերը: [57]

One can see that the text unit “in the heart of the bush” is transformed into a single word, in the result of which in the target language the idiom lost its expressiveness and moves from the level of word combination toward a level of word. Such a way of translation enables the translator to condense the translated information if it suits the requirements of the target language. Here the contextual synonym in translating works perfectly and overlaps the whole meaning of the phrase.

Idioms with the fruit (also berry) components

• **Fruit (also berries):** a product of plant growth; the usually edible reproductive body of a seed plant; a succulent plant part. Berry is defined as a pulpy and usually edible fruit (such as a strawberry, raspberry, or checkerberry) of small size irrespective of its structure (Merriam Webster dictionary).

(As) *brown as a berry* - արևանխանձ (շականակագույն) հատապտղի պես

“*Brown as a berry*” is an idiomatic expression with simile entities and the definition is “having a very dark skin from being in the sun” (Collins dictionary). The idiomatic expression appears twice in Geoffrey Chaucer’s *Canterbury Tales*, dating from the 1380s, firstly in the Prologue (“His palfrey was as brown as is a berye”, referring to a horse ridden by a monk) and then in the unfinished *Cook’s Tale* as a description of the cook (“Broun as a berye, a propre short felawe”). The latter may have the meaning that is used nowadays in modern English. However, there is an issue with the components brown and berry together, as there are no brown berries. It is thought that in the English of the time berry could refer to a nut, but there’s no suggestion in the Oxford English Dictionary that people used it that way. The Dictionary does remark that in Old English, four centuries before Chaucer, berry was most commonly used of grapes, but it would be difficult to describe any variety of a grape as brown. Curiously, brown was also used of armour or glass to mean shining bright — “sword of brown steel”. Some berries are shiny, but it is unlikely that brown in this sense was used of a person’s face.

Ancient writers seemed to be insensitive to colour and emphasised light and dark in preference to hues.

This expression may have been influenced by other languages and their understanding of the colour “brown”, for example, in Swedish, “brun” could mean dark-coloured or black, dark red, or reddish-brown; in Old French “brun” meant a dark colour between red and black; Old High German “brûn” could mean dark-coloured. This seems like the most probable origin (Worldwidewords). Example:

He was as brown as a berry, and walked softly, with almost a catlike tread. In marked contrast with his sunburned skin were his eyes — blue, deep blue, but keen and sharp as a pair of gimlets. [14]

Տղան արևանխանձ էր հատապտղի պես և քայլում էր մեղմասահ, կատվի պես թեթև. Արևից վառված դեմքի հակապատկերն էին կազմում նրա խոր ընկած կապույտ աչքերը, որոնք նայում էին պրպտող ու թափանցող հայացքով: [626]

It becomes evident that the sentence has been much domesticated; the translator has successfully preserved the style of the idiomatic expression in the target language. Both in English and Armenian the simile has the same connotation and the translator artfully found the most appropriate simile in the target language.

• **Apple:** the fleshy, usually rounded red, yellow, or green edible pome fruit of a usually cultivated tree (genus *Malus*) of the rose family (Merriam Webster dictionary).

Apple of discord – կռվախնձոր

“*Apple of discord*” means “a subject of contention and envy” (Merriam Webster Dictionary). The idiom comes from the expression *the golden apple of discord* that was created by Eris, the Goddess of Discord. Zeus had thrown a wedding, after Eris found out that she was not invited, she crashed the wedding and threw the apple inscribed with the word “for the fairest”. The goddesses all fought over the apple, but it came down to Hera, Aphrodite and Athena. They asked Zeus to decide who received the apple and he told them that Paris of Troy was to choose the fairest. Each of the goddesses offered him a gift for the apple. Paris of Troy gave the apple to Aphrodite. The rest is known, all due to the golden apple of discord, the Trojan War had begun (Myths and Folklore Wiki). The following example is from the famous novel *Jane Eyre* by Charlotte Brontë.

“Forgive me the words, St. John; but it is your own fault that I have been roused to speak so unguardedly. You have introduced a topic on which our natures are at variance— a topic we should never discuss: the very name of love is an apple of discord between us. If the reality were required, what should we do? How should we feel? My dear cousin, abandon your scheme of marriage—forget it.” [623]

- Ներեցեք ինձ այդ խոսքերի համար, Սենտ Ջոն. Բայց դուք ինքներդ եք մեղավոր, որ դրանք այդպես անզգույշ դուրս թռան բերանիցս: Դուք շոշափեցիք այնպիսի թեմա, որի նկատմամբ մեր հայացքները խիստ տարբերվում են իրարից, մի թեմա, որի մասին մենք չպետք է վիճենք. հենց սեր հասկացողությունը հանդիսանում է կռվախնձոր մեր միջև. ապա ի՞նչ կանեինք մենք, եթե այդ հարցը լրջորեն կանգնած լիներ մեր

վիջու: Ի՞նչ կզգայիսք մենք: Միրելի կուզեն, հրաժարվեք ամուսնության ձեր ծրագրից, սնուցեք: [556]

The idiom “apple of discord” is translated “կովախնձոր”, which is the Armenian equivalent of the expression. From the above-given example we can obviously see that the original form and meaning of the phrase is retained.

The apple of one’s eye – աչքի խնձոր, աչքի լույս

“The apple of one’s eye” is defined as “the person who someone loves most and is very proud of” (Cambridge dictionary). The phrase is from the Bible, in which it appears in four books of The Old Testament. The first use of the phrase appears in Deuteronomy 32:10, which reads “He found him in a desert land, and in the howling waste of the wilderness; he encircled him, he cared for him, he kept him as the apple of his eye.” A more literal translation of the Hebrew is actually “little man of his eye,” which probably refers to the reflection of oneself that one sees in the eye of another person. In early English translations of the Bible, however, the phrase appears as “apple of his eye.” This probably developed from the Anglo-Saxon word “ar-pel,” meaning both “apple” and “pupil.” Thus, the phrase developed into “apple of one’s eye” and retained the meaning of something treasured (Deseret).

This example is also from “Jane Eyre”.

Mr. Rochester continued blind the first two years of our union; perhaps it was that circumstance that drew us so very near—that knit us so very close: for I was then his vision, as I am still his right hand. Literally, I was (what he often called me) the apple of his eye. [688]

Մեր ամուսնության առաջին երկու տարին վիստր Ռոչեստերը շարունակում էր կույր մնալ: Գուցե այդ հանգամանքն էր, որ մեզ հատկապես մոտեցրեց, սերտ կերպով կապեց իրար հետ. Ես այն ժամանակ նրա տեսողությունն էի, ինչպես մինչև հիմա շարունակում եմ մնալ նրա աջ ձեռքը: Բառացի իմաստով (ինչպես նա ինքն ինձ հաճախ անվանում էր) նրա **աչքի խնձորն** էի: [614]

“I was the apple of his eye” is translated in a similar way “նրա աչքի խնձորն էի”. We can also find an Armenian expression “աչքի լույս”, which can be defined a functional equivalent to the phrase under investigation. This idiomatic expression as well as the previous one are labeled as universal types being originated from the same source.

• **Fig:** a sweet, soft, purple, or green fruit with many seeds, or a tree on which these grow (Cambridge dictionary).

Not give a fig about/for something – անտարբեր լինել մի բանի նկատմամբ

The expression means to not care at all about something (Macmillan dictionary). This usage of fig goes back to the earliest days of modern English (or the end of Middle English). To care a fig is to care almost nothing; not to care a fig, or give a fig.

‘Who would not be the Rizzio of so divine a Mary?’

‘**A fig for Rizzio!**’ cried she, tossing her head with all its curls, as she moved to the piano. ‘It is my opinion the fiddler David must have been an insipid sort of fellow; I like black Bothwell better: to my mind a man is nothing without a spice of the devil in him; and history may say what it will of James Hepburn, but I have a notion, he was just the sort of wild, fierce, bandit hero whom I could have consented to gift with my hand.’ [271]

- Ո՞վ չի ցանկանա այդպիսի աստվածային Մերիի Ռիչչիոն լինել:

- Թողե՛ք ձեր Ռիչչիոն, - բղավեց նա, թափ տալով իր գանգուրները և շարժվելով դեպի դաշնամուրը: - Իմ կարծիքով այդ ջութակահար Դավիդը անձաշակ մարդ է եղել, սև Բոթվելն ինձ ավելի է դուր գալիս. ես գտնում եմ, որ տղամարդը ոչնչություն է, եթե նրա մեջ սատանայական որևէ բան չկա. թող պատմությունն ինչ ուզում է ասի Ջեյմս Հեյբերնի մասին, բայց, ինձ թվում է, թե նա եղել է վայրենի, կատաղի, այնպիսի մի ավազակ, որին ես կհամաձայնեի ձեռքս տալ: [239]

As it can be noticed in the original text the phrase is found in an affirmative form, and retains its positive structuring in the target text. The transformation made by the author is usually performed for producing negative evaluation in a positive context; specifically it expresses indignation, annoyance towards the speaker’s utterance.

The expression is changed in this example taken from the novel Jane Eyre - *a fig for ...*, in this case “*A fig for Rizzio*”, which indicated ignorance by the speaker. The Armenian translation is “Թողե՛ք ձեր Ռիչչիոն”, meaning “let go of the topic/ ignore Rizzio”. In our opinion, the translation strategy is more paraphrasing than that of similar sense and dissimilar form.

• **Grapes:** a smooth-skinned juicy light green or deep red to purplish black berry eaten dried or fresh as a fruit or fermented to produce wine (Merriam Webster Dictionary).

Sour grapes – թթու խաղող

The expression as such meanings as - “disparagement of something that has proven unattainable” (Merriam-Webster dictionary) “If you describe someone’s behavior or opinion as sour grapes, you mean that that person is angry because they have not got or achieved something that they wanted” (Cambridge dictionary).

The phrase “sour grapes” originated in Aesop’s Fables, in a story called “The Fox and the Grapes.” A fox sees a juicy bunch of grapes hanging from a trellised vine and yearns to have them. After several failed attempts to reach the grapes, the fox realizes he’ll never get them, and walks away. In an attempt to save his reputation and cure his smarting ego, the fox says the grapes were sour anyway, so he never really wanted them (Vinepair). The following example is from “The Professor” by Charlotte Brontë.

“No, you are not content; you see beauty always turning its back on you; you are mortified and then you sneer. I verily believe all that is desirable on earth — wealth, reputation, love — will for ever to you be the ripe grapes on the high trellis: you’ll look up at them; they will tantalize in you the lust of the eye; but they are out of reach: you have not the address to fetch a ladder, and you’ll go away calling them sour.” [188]

There is an Armenian proverb from an old fable «Խաղողը աղվեսի դնչին չհասավ, սասց՝ թթու է», also used as «աղվեսի բերանը խաղողին չի հասնում, սսում է՝ խակ է». They both have the same meaning and the same architecture with the same constituents: “sour” – “թթու” , and “grapes” – “խաղող”.

To sum up, idioms are the particularly important part of the English and Armenian languages. More than a half of native speakers support this statement, mainly because they consider idioms to be their cultural heritage. Idioms are integral part of a language which makes our speech more colourful and authentically native.

Botanical idioms of the English and Armenian languages possess a high interlingual equivalence that is explained by the fact that botanical components are in the high-frequency vocabulary of the contrasted languages and their high phrase-forming activity increases the degree of interlingual equivalence.

In fact, the same botanical components can have different effect and notion behind it in the same language and in contrastive languages. The results show that interpretations on the relation holding between the denotative and connotative meanings of the idioms under investigation is cultural-specific.

It is worth mentioning that both languages and cultures have surprisingly similar concepts about certain botanical components with, plant, vegetable and fruit constituents (six idiomatic pairs in contrastive languages were similar in meaning and contained the same botanical constituent). Therefore, it can be stated that both languages have many universal framings within their culture. This may be the result of the influence by Greek mythology, the Bible, prominent historical events, wide international communication, etc.

Translating idiomatic expressions is a difficult and tricky process; however, it is possible to carry it out by implementing appropriate strategies and techniques of translation taking into consideration the situation, readership, genre, etc. In the below presented chart can be observed functional frequency of techniques of translation.

The translation of English idioms is beautifully (nicely) in proportion with its Armenian. There are also cases that are completely out of proportion with their counterparts.

The investigation showed that there are two main ways of translation of botanical idioms from English into Armenian: paraphrasing, similar meaning dissimilar form. There also have been found cases of omission, and even some idioms have been translated. The compensational technique of translation has not been found during the investigation.

As we can observe, out of nineteen idioms under investigation five idioms have positive stance, six idioms have negative stance and eight idioms are neutral.

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**THE GREAT NIZAMI. POET'S LIFE.
PART I**

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7271273>

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Abstract

The year 2021 marks the 900th anniversary of the birth of Nizami Ganjavi. Azerbaijan has the honorable but also challenging task of commemorating this momentous anniversary of the genius Azerbaijani poet in a dignified manner.

Keywords: curious, monograph, talent, literature.

The significance of Nizami's work goes beyond the boundaries of Azerbaijani literature proper. His works are amazing achievement of human genius like works of great masters of the world: Firdausi, Dante, Shakespeare, etc.

We need to make his poems available to all the peoples of our immense planet by the time we celebrate his birth anniversary. This will require a lot of hard work, because, unfortunately, so far not much has been done to avenge the study of Nizami, as in general with regard to the study of the literatures of the East. It is currently impossible to show the entire richness and depth of Nizami's work. It is particularly difficult to do so in a popular presentation, which necessarily requires a long and painstaking research work to precede it.

The present article is one of the first attempts to introduce the life and work of Nizami to a wider audience. Therefore, it cannot aim at solving all the prob-

lems associated with the study of his works. Any attempt at a comprehensive coverage of Nizami's work can be accomplished only in the form of a voluminous monograph, but not in the framework of a journal article. At this stage the task is more modest. I just want to familiarize the readers with the basic facts, to show who Nizami was, what his works consist of and why this work has such an immense value.

The XI-XII centuries A.D. is one of the most tumultuous and turbulent periods in the history of the Near East. If by the beginning of the 10th century the spread of the Caliphate was over and the local dynasties that had departed from it on all fringes were again vigorously trying to occupy the dominant position, then by the beginning of the 11th century the Seljuks, who were moving on their horses with fabulous speed and were everywhere throwing their masters aside, began to influx from the steppes of Central Asia.